

DEFORESTATION AND HOW TO SAVE THE GREEN PLANET.**Kdirbaeva Aksungul Rustemovna**3rd year student of the English language and literature

Berdakh Karakalpak State University

Abstract: The word deforestation is something that can be comprehended as a big trouble to nature. As it means to reduce the green piece of our Planet by cutting trees and turning forests into naked place. Those naked places are probably used for people`s sake , still it does not mean that people have the right to destroy forest . Since the loss of trees and vegetations can lead to several serious effects not only to local but also to more tremendous and global climate changes.

Key words: Deforestation, hurricanes, climate changes, environmentalist, livestock, 800gt of carbon dioxide, plantations, agriculture, human-being, photosynthesis, Aral Sea, Antarctica.

Introduction

There are two causes of deforestation. First natural reason like hurricane , climate change, acid rains and so on. Another reason why this disaster is occurring are by the hands of human-being. People from ancient times cut down forest with the hope of extraction of minerals, to feed themselves , to make papers and to use the land for farmlands .

Now in planet inhabits more than 8.12 billions of people. This amount would not exist if there was not deforestation.

One of the main sources of food is considered to be forests. According to British environmentalist Norman Myers , 5% of deforestation in Tropics is used for grazing livestock, 19% is the cause of timber harvesting , 22% - due to the expansion of oil palm plantations and 54%- because of slash-and-burn agriculture . In Africa is found almost third of all arid regions of the world , In Latin America, Australia and Asia are also widespread deforestation . 6 million

hectares are wholly destroyed per year , more than 20 million hectares reduce their productivity.

Russia takes the first place in having the biggest territory of forest (809 million hectares) . Brasilia is in the second - 520 million hectares. Then Canada- 310 , USA which has 304 million hectares of forest land. If there were more arborists- people who are against of cutting forest trees , in your country too , it would be possible that your country would also be one of the leading countries.

The Environmental Organisation (WWF) has compiled a ranking of the countries that takes leading place in destruction of forests around the world . The first place in this rating was given China Which is responsible for 24% of Destroyed tropical forests Worldwide.

Main body

Consequences of deforestation are several. It can be **global warming**, often called one of the main reasons of increasing greenhouse effect. For this reason Antarctica is melting and melting day by day. If this continues like this , the 19% of world population`s life will be at risk. Another well-noun impacts of deforestation is **air pollution**. As atmosphere of Earth includes carbon dioxide in the form of nearly 800gt of carbon. In ground-plants, big amount of which constitutes approximately 550gt of carbon , in simple words trees and vegetations absorb contaminated air and produce more fresh and pure air. And in the course of life they confiscates carbon dioxide from Earth`s atmosphere in the process of photosynthesis . However , old trees throw back the carbons to atmosohere , so they should be recycled and new forests ought to be planted. What is more , it can cause heat stroke, injury or death from extreme weather and diseases including cholera, dengue, and malaria. These serious diseases can end one`s life. Deforestation will not stop in hurting people`s life or climate , but it can be the reason why now most of the sorts of animals and flowers have completely or partly disappeared(extinct animals like : Woolly Mammoth, West African Black Rhinoceros, Sabre-Toothed Tiger, Irish Elk , Tasmanian Tiger; extinct

flowers including Silphium , Cooksonia , Saint Helena mountain bush , Vallerianella affins, Cry violet, Toromiro tree Hawaii chaff flower , Franklin tree). All of this by human mistake. So now created ecology protection organizations and committees to prevent process of deforestation!

Contention with deforestation is one of the direct actions of environmental protection . In some levels of international rights, in state levels and social events connected with forest protection . Another way is struggling with forest fires by establishing Installation of fire lanes and security guards .

The policies, practices , and mechanisms used to conserve and promote the diverse ecological, economic , social and cultural functions of plantations, forests and woodlands suffer from major deficiencies. A lot of actions are made by government but it is not enough to reach immediate success . Therefore, it would better to call everyone to protect nature and reduce actions of hurting forests.

Steps to prevent deforestation. If everyone starts reckoning about planting at least one tree , it will be vital step to rescue our Greenland . Also, using less paper , not buying products containing palm oil, raising awareness, joining to ecologic projects, practicing ecoforestry , stop burning firewood.

To justify that planting tree can save «green» planet let`s take as an example , **Aral Sea**, which is now becoming Aral Khum (desert). In 1961 Aral Sea level started to decrease at a rate of 20 to 80-90 cm per year. Now Eastern Aral is completely dry. Despite the fact that Aral Sea is located in Central Asia, it still influences badly to worldwide climate . So world organizations such as, UN are in the process of solving problem with Aral disaster . And they made up mind to keep the dust that emits desert of Aral by planting so-called saxaul trees. And it really worked . With the help of trees even desert dust can be kept from effecting to atmosphere.

Conclusion

«The death of the forest is the end of our life» -, said by Dorothy Stang . These words should be kept in mind of everyone. And everyone should have a clue about ecology and what can worth one tree in the forest . Perhaps in this tree is living a group of Insects or birds. Perhaps this actions lead to some sorts of animal extinction . Unfortunately people are not aware of trouble that caused by deforestation since they were not educated to ecology. It would be the best choice if every pupil and student would be given an opportunity to gain knowledge and keep up with ecologic problems like deforestation, global warming and so on. They do not see that one nature issue can lead to another bigger and more severe problems . Despite the fact that people used to consider that animals are predators and they can hurt or even kill people if we do not control them . It is only because they reckon more about how to feed themselves . It seems that if people do not control themselves too, they can be the reason why our «green» planet is being destroyed. People are the ones who are destroying those predator animals life . What is the difference? At least people can protect themselves from animals , but animals cannot . If people is smarter than «animals» it does not mean that they can do anything to them and to nature. Forest is also the home for animals . So be aware of every consequence before deciding to hurt something . Stop hurting the Nature and start adding a little bit of your stuff to «green» Planet since every piece of nature was created for a reason and people have no power to change these reasons by using them to own advantage or they have to else be ready to answer for all mistakes that are done by you.

References

Michael Williams. Deforesting the Earth: From Prehistory To Global Crisis , An Abridgment. University of Chicago Press, 2010. -561 c. – ISBN 0226899055

<https://education.nationalgeographic.org>

<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>

<https://www.theworldcounts.com>

Aber , J. D., Botkin , D.B., and Melillo, J.M (1978). Predicting the effects of different harvesting regimes on forest floor dynamics in northern hardwoods . Canadian Journal for Forest Research ,8(3) , 306-315.

Goodale ,C.L (20002). Inorganic nitrogen losses from forested ecosystem in response to physical , chemical, biotic, and climatic pertubations. Ecosystems, 5(7), 0648-0658.

Aerts, R (0997). Climate , leaf litter chemistry and leaf litter decomposition in terrestrial ecosystems: a triangular relationship, Oikos , 79,439-449

<https://www.un.org>

<https://ru.m.wikipedia.org>